

SECOND YEAR OF MONITORING OF 'CANDIDATUS LIBERIBACTER SOLANACEARUM' IN CARROT FIELD TRIALS

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Since the first detection in 2008 of '*Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*' (CaLsol) in Spain (in Villena, Alicante), this pathogen has caused year after year variable economic losses in carrot production for the fresh market. In this area, the transmission of the bacterium has been reported mainly by the insect vectors *Bactericera trigonica* and sometimes by *Trioza apicalis*. As part of the objective of providing practical solutions for the management and containment of the diseases associated with this pathogen, challenges with different treatments based on one horticultural mineral oil and three biopesticides were performed by partner 16 (Certis Europe), throughout the second half of 2017, to test their efficacy against vectors and CaLsol damages.

A carrot seed lot of 'Soprano F1' cultivar, tested negative for CaLsol, was sown in two open air plots, close to each other. Each plot was divided into 24 squares of 12 x 36 m² each. Four treatments against insect vectors were tested: maltodextrine, natural pyrethrins, paraffin oil and the entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria bassiana*, using acetamiprid as a compound of known activity against insect vectors. Each treatment was applied several times in four squares per field randomly distributed, and four received no treatment. At harvest, the plants were inspected for CaLsol symptomatology and ten samples of carrot leaves per square were analysed by real-time PCR for CaLsol detection in both fields. These samples were also analysed for the universal detection of '*Candidatus Phytoplasma*' (CaPhy) and for *Spiroplasma citri*.

The samples that had been treated with any of the assayed compounds showed an average level of CaLsol infection similar to untreated plants (81-91% positive samples), but only 5-10% of the samples showed symptomatology compatible with that described for CaLsol or CaPhy. Interestingly, all CaLsol-positive samples analyzed were also positive for CaPhy, while *Spiroplasma citri* was not detected in any of them. All these data suggest that the field and environmental conditions assayed were not appropriate for expression of the bacterial symptomatology and/or the treatments were playing a role in stimulating plant defences or other mechanisms.